

Research

Model to improve the dimensions of logistics performance in Asian countries

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Accepted: 1 July, 2020; **Online:** 4 July, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3930252>

Abstract: The purpose of this study is to examine the impact of global competitiveness index (GCI) on the dimensions of logistics performance (LP) model for Asia countries. Panel data on 37 Asian countries over 2007-2018 were regressed under hierarchical regression analyses. Core variable GCI along with two control variables has been used in the study. Findings generated from the regression demonstrate that six dimensions of logistics performance of Asian economies could be improved by implementing global competitiveness index. Six individual models on efficiency of customs clearance process, transport related infrastructure, competitive price shipments, quality of logistics services, frequency of shipments, and tracing and tracking are statistically significant and execute more than 65% variations while the impact on competitive price shipments is mild. So, the model significance & statistical change in R^2 & adjusted R^2 signifies the contribution and the importance of GCI in context of policy implementation to improve Asian logistics performance taking GCI as the catalyst for LP.

Keywords: Logistics performance; Global competitiveness index; Asian countries; Dimensions

1 Background of the study

Efficient and competitive logistics services are vital to boost the developing Asia's comparative advantages as a global logistics hub. Logistics performance (LP) is considered to be the fundamental building block of economic hub development. Well-functioning domestic and international logistics is a precondition of national competitiveness (Arvis et al., 2018). Logistics performance in terms of trade and transport related infrastructure, customers services, timeliness, competency of services, trace & tracking, frequency of shipments & facilities of interventions, policies and public sectors services across the region still varies. Efficient, reliable and safe logistics services & infrastructure are very crucial to regional integration. Both public and private sectors play vital role in building infrastructure and developing logistics services in Asia. Higher

logistics performance arguments supply chain efficiency and competitive advantages (Kwok, 2019; Shang, 2004). A country's ability to trade globally depends on the access to efficient logistics services (Önsel Ekici et al., 2016). Logistics services and performance in Asia for each economy has been broadened now. So, the present study is conducted to observe the variation of dimensions of LP using global competitiveness index (GCI).

Logistics performance has become a fundamental factor for the generation of competitive advantages and creation of value, through the planning, implementation and control of processes linked to physical flows, and the integration of processes along the supply chain (Alarcón, Antón, and Lozano 2012). The efficient management of logistics services & performance allow reducing the costs related to the goods flow through the supply chain (Alarcón et al., 2012; Bookbinder & Tan, 2003). Many logistics companies are looking to respond to the development of new transport corridors; especially Asian logistics hub is very effective in this regard. Companies are moving towards new trading and investment policies undertaken by the economies. More and more multinationals logistics companies are entering into the domestic market of emerging economies in Asia (Ruske et al., 2010). It's a clear beacon for Asian logistics hub that is going to accelerate more advantages in global market. But the major concern regarding Asian logistics performance is the development of infrastructure, expansion of market, improvement in macroeconomic factors and innovation of technology. Logistics performance in many developed countries have been optimized & improved in the past. Consequently, international trade and transportations are getting privileges from logistics performance sectors there. LP in Asia however, should be modified and the countries must come out of the cultivation of traditional activities to develop LP. The influence of global competitiveness score can be taken into account to explain the performance of the countries.

Asian economies from emerging markets will not gain significant market share as the developed countries, even low-tech logistics solutions are not perceived as a viable route to win market share (Ruske et al., 2010). Improved logistics services & hub development can play prominent role & challenge of providing better services as countries are moving towards more complex and higher-value manufacturing trend (Brooks, 2008). Global competitiveness index (GCI) can play significant role in improving Asian logistics performance. The 12 competitive indicators defined by the World Economic Forum (WEF) tell us about the country's development level (Çemberci et al., 2015). These indicators have positive influence on country's economy, transportation and logistics services infrastructure as well. GCI has been considered in the model as mediator to improve LP by Çemberci et al., 2015, Ekici et al., 2019, Beysenbaev & Dus, 2019 in their study. Previous researches done on Asian logistics performance hardly capture the impact of global competitiveness indicators on performance development. Most of the researches have been done more commonly at micro-logistics level rather than at the level of global logistics (Beysenbaev & Dus, 2020). Some researchers showed the mediator impact of global competitiveness index & some others used the 12 indicators of GCI to link up with logistics performance on individual country.

To the best of our knowledge, no research has yet been done on the development of LP model for Asian economies using GCI. Hence, Global competitiveness score has been undertaken into consideration in our present study as the major explanatory indicator in the regression process to develop the dimension of the individual model of logistics performance indicators. This is gone to be the first benchmark using panel data of 37 Asian economics to improve model for Asian logistics performance evaluation. So, the main intention of this study is to extract the degree of influence of global competitiveness index on logistics performance indicators, identified by the World Bank. It will further contribute to the implementation of policies and measure should be taken by the countries. The next part of the paper is designed as- literature review in 2nd section, conceptual framework in 3rd section, research methodologies in 4th section, result analysis & discussion in 5th section and conclusion in the final section.

2 Related works reviews

Tree-augmented naive Bayesian network model was used to develop a roadmap for policymakers in improving the logistics performance of countries (Önsel Ekici et al., 2019). The study analyzed the effect of the competitiveness pillars of the Global Competitiveness Index (GCI) on logistics performances & showed that technological readiness, innovation, infrastructure, market size & higher education and training can facilitate to improve logistics performance. Undertaking hierarchical regression analysis, moderator impact of global competitiveness index on logistics performance has been discussed (Çemberci et al., 2015). This study has found significant impact of GCI on logistics performance. Survey research has found the relationships among the logistics performances capabilities, logistics performance; quality practices of logistics performance measurement and financial performance those help to identify opportunities for improvements of logistics performance (Abu Bakar et al., 2014; Shang, 2004). Sustainability of operational logistics performance of OECD nations has been analyzed using Data envelopment analysis (DEA) and a comparison between the nationals ranking has been achieved (Rashidi & Cullinane, 2019). However, comparative study of logistics competitiveness has been analyzed by Alarcon et al. 2012; Yildiz, 2017; Bookbinder & Tin, 2002. Interaction between logistics performance & global competitiveness of Turkey has been discussed using Artificial Neural Network (ANN) & Cumulative Belief Degrees (CBD) to develop the basic strategies to be adopted by the government to achieve the targeted level of logistics performance (Önsel Ekici et al., 2016).

Proposal for improving logistics performances of 159 countries have been demonstrated based on the analysis of global competitiveness index both in qualitative and quantitative approach by Beysenbaev & Dus. The study proposed a modified index to evaluate logistics performance (Beysenbaev & Dus, 2020). Review on the logistics management & collaboration in Asia has found that more collaboration at the institutional, national, and international levels is needed to progress in logistics capabilities in Asia (Yen-chun et al., 2017). The impact of the validity of logistics performance of export-led growth (ELG) hypothesis on 23 Asian economies is examined using Cobb-Douglas production function and found that the export-led growth hypothesis is valid and significantly related with logistics performances (Tang & Abosedra,

2019). Relationship between intra-firm resources and logistics performance has been visualized using Structural Equation Model (SEM) to demonstrate their impact on logistics capabilities (Yang & Lirn, 2017). Logistics services quality of East Asia of international freight has been evaluated in empirical analysis taking quality function deployment approach and the result revealed that all the factors of logistics performance relating to the customers services may have impact on overall logistics performance (Huang et al., 2019).

3 Conceptual frameworks

In order to develop the model of LP, we conducted this research treating global competitiveness score as the core explanatory variable while volume of trade (% of GDP) and dummy variable (port facilities) are used as control variables. The six dimensions of logistics performance determined by the WB are the efficiency of customs clearance process (ECCP), quality of transport & trade related infrastructure (QTTINFRT), competitive price shipments (CPS), competency and quality of logistics services (CQLS), frequency of shipments (FS) and consignments tracking (CT). The dimensions of the logistics performance scores have been defined on the basis of the evaluation of multi-criteria of each country. LP is an interactive benchmarking tool to measure performance along with logistics supply chain within a country (Vale, 2017). It helps to identify the challenge and opportunities for trade logistics of the countries (World Bank, <https://lpi.worldbank.org/>). Research showed that LP is statistically significantly related to the volume of trade. Because facilitating trade and transport is at the core of stimulating economic development, several countries have developed comprehensive national logistics strategies (Arvis et al. 2018). Success of bilateral trade depends on goods transportation & logistics cost, customs and duties (Hausman et al., 2013). Efficient logistics services facilitate the mobility of products, ensuring their safety and speed as well as reduction in cost when trading them among countries (Martí et al., 2014). So, logistics performance & supply chain reliability are major concern for traders and those are positively related to volume of trade (Arvis et al. 2014). So, conceptual model (Figure-1) developed to visualize the impact of trade, GCI and Dummy variable (port facilities) on logistics performance (LP).

Figure 1: conceptual model for dimension of logistics performance

Moreover, the importance of ports facilities are not confined only to cargo handling but also includes the stipulations of better logistics services to satisfy the increasing demand of SCM globally (Munim & Schramm, 2018). Port development not only supports the shipping activities, also updates the trade and transport related infrastructure towards supply chain facilities and logistics activities. Ports performance has become more complex due to the fact that ports work today as nodes of global logistics chains (Vale, 2017). Global development of SC increased the pressure on port related logistics performance (Notteboom & Rodrigue, 2005; Pettit & Beresford, 2009). Availability and accessibility of factors like higher education, macroeconomic stability, labor market, technological adaptation, institutions, market size, financial development, infrastructure and education have influence on LP. Therefore, GCI with trade volume & port facilities have been considered in dimension of logistics performance model.

4 Research methodologies

4.1 Data collection & reliability test

To develop model for the dimension of logistics performance, we have collected data on 37 Asian countries (Appendix-A). Three types of data- logistics performance data, global competitiveness score of global competitiveness index (GCI) & trade volume (% of GDP) of each country have been selected for this study. Data on logistics performance indicators & trade volume (% of GDP) have been collected from World Bank (WB) database where global competitiveness indicators extracted from World Economic Forum (WEF). Logistics performance indicators are measured on Likert scale from 1-5; while 1 stands for lower level of the performance and 5 for the highest. Global competitiveness scores are measured on likert scale 1-7; 1 for low and 7 for the high. Time duration used in the study ranges from 2007 to 2018 with gaps. However, we also have used a dummy variable of port facilities- 1 for countries which have port and 0 for countries which don't have port. The dummy variable along with trade volume is used as control variable in first block of regression process. Variables used for the study are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Variables list used for the research

Variables	Abbreviation
Efficiency of customs clearance process	ECCP
Quality of trade and transport related infrastructure	QTTINFRT
Competitive price shipments	CPS
Competence and quality of logistics services	CQLS
Frequency of shipments	FS
Consignments tracing and tracking	CT
Global competitiveness Index	GCI
Trade volume (% of GDP)	TR
Dummy variable	DV

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics & the Pearson 2-tailed correlation of the variables. Positive mean values and significant correlation of the indicators imply the internal consistency

of the data sets shown in table 2. All the variables have the high correlation significant at 0.01 or 0.05 levels.

Table 2: Descriptive statistics and correlation matrix

	N.	Mean	Std. D.	ECCP	QTTINFRT	CPS	CQLS	FS	CT	GCI	TR	DV
ECCP	218	2.7228	.57806	1								
QTTINFRT	218	2.8094	.68662	.939**	1							
CPS	218	2.9227	.52314	.846**	.878**	1						
CQLS	218	2.8821	.59628	.922**	.940**	.872**	1					
FS	218	3.3494	.56083	.837**	.878**	.836**	.876**	1				
CT	218	2.9498	.60962	.888**	.924**	.878**	.924**	.894**	1			
GCI	212	4.3830	.67801	.731**	.753**	.638**	.709**	.686**	.708**	1		
TR	221	4.3988	.71476	.334**	.284**	.280**	.244**	.241**	.241**	.259**	1	
DV	222	0.7027	.45810	.618**	.631**	.637**	.643**	.638**	.660**	.353**	.168*	1
Valid N. (list wise)	208											

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2 tailed).

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2 tailed).

4.2 Hierarchical regression analysis

Hierarchical regression analysis is adopted to analyze each dimension of logistics performance in this study. Because Hierarchical regression attempts to improve standards regression estimates by adding a second-stage "prior" regression to an ordinary model (Witte et al., 1994). The variations across groups can be estimated easily in a hierarchical regression model & it gives more stable and plausible estimates (Chi & Voss, 2005; Witte et al., 1994). Hierarchical regression is often performed when the extra amount of variance accounted for a dependent variable by a specific independent variable is the main focus of interest (Cohen & Cohen, 1985). Moreover, undertaking hierarchical regression analysis, the model in the first stage could be controlled inputting some control factors. In the present analysis, we input dummy and trade volume (% of GDP) in the first block to get the authentic performance in the final block of the regression. A diagram hierarchical regression analysis is presented in figure 2 outlaying two blocks and the change of R^2 between two blocks, that is the variation accounted for a dependent variable for the dimension of the model improvement.

Figure 2: A framework of Hierarchical Regression analysis

Being a multiple linear regression, more variables are added to the model in different steps called “blocks” in Hierarchical regression analysis. It is statistically done to control certain variables to see whether adding variables significantly can improve a model’s ability to predict the outcome variables or to investigate a moderating effect of a variable. In this regard, we have developed six individual models to predict dimension of six logistics performance indicators.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} ECCP_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ ECCP_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} QTTINFRT_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ QTTINFRT_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 T + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} CPS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ CPS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} CQLS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ CQLS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} FS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ FS_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} CT_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \\ CT_{i,t} &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 DV + \beta_2 TR_{i,t} + \beta_3 GCI_{i,t} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

Here ECCP, QTTINFRT, CPS, CQLS, FS & CT indicate the logistics performance variables presented in the table 1 and DV for dummy variable, TR for trade (% of GDP), GCI for global competitiveness index, and ‘ε’ for error terms of each individual country where ‘t’ stands for time duration and ‘i’ for Asian countries.

Prior to conducting regression, sample adequacy and reliability have been checked. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Sampling Adequacy test have been used as reference value for the selection of variables for factor analysis to extract the loadings of the variables. KMO value got from the test is 0.94 which is greater the recommended level (0.6) presented in table 3. This bears the proofs of data reliability and stability. Chi-square for Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity is 2397 at 0.000 significant levels which is mandatory for the stability test. It indicates the significant relation among the variables. Furthermore, we have checked Cronbach’s alpha score with 93.7% of valid cases (208 valid cases out of total 222 cases, excluded 14 cases, table-4) to be confirm of the data stability before running the regression. The reason for this is the missing cases of some data sets. The moderate alpha level is 0.6-0.7 but more than 0.7 is the best. The overall alpha score we incurred in the study is 0.93, much greater than the acceptable level (table 4).

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett’s Test of sample adequacy

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.94
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2397
	df	36
	Sig.	.000

To increase the validity of hierarchical regression analysis, we have adopted factor analysis and obtained factor loadings of the variables to observe the degree of impact of each variable showed in table 4 and the same process in hierarchical regression is used by (Bringula et al., 2018; Chen et al., 2019; Kim et al., 2018). All variables except trade volume produced remarkable level of impacts indicating high scale composite reliability for the study. ECCP counted for 94% of the variation, QTTINFRT for 96%, CPS for 91%, CQLS for 96%, FS for 92%, CT for 96%, GCI for 78%, DV for 70% and TR for 32%.

Table 4: Result of factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha score with case processing summery

	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha test			Alpha score
		Case processing summery			
		Number	%		
ECCP	0.948				
QTTINFRT	0.969				
CPS	0.916				
CQLS	0.961	Valid cases	208	93.7	
FS	0.927	Excluded	14	6.3	
CT	0.961	Total cases	222	100	
GCI	0.779				
TR	0.322				
DV	0.693				

We further considered the question of panel unit root issue in the data sets that may raise stationary problem. Economic theory requires all variables to be stationary if the regressions are to be realistic (Aldakhil et al., 2018; Azam et al., 2016; Hasan, 2017; Hasan & Nishi, 2019). There are many panel unit root test for the last few decades. Among them Levin and Lin (1992, 1993), Quah (1992, 1994), Maddala and Wu (1999), Im et al. (2003, 1997), Hadri (2000) and Levin et al. (2002) are most commonly used. However, panel unit root test is a continuation of the univariate unit root test identified earlier but it possesses low power like ADF-test (Said & Dickey, 1984). For this purpose we have chosen Levin-Lin Chu (LLC), Im Pesaran & Shin (IPS) and PP Fisher chi-square test presented in table 5.

Table 5: Result of panel unit root test summery

Variables	LLC	IPS	PP
	Level	Level	Level
ECCP	-13.44 (.000)	-3.40 (.000)	160.6 (.000)
QTTINFRT	-20.15 (.000)	-7.25 (.000)	229.16 (.000)
CPS	-28.35 (.000)	-6.53 (.000)	193.01 (.000)
CQLS	-17.02 (.000)	-4.27 (.000)	171.33 (.000)
FS	-24.47 (.000)	-7.03 (.000)	212.82 (.000)
CT	-21.26 (.000)	-6.63 (.000)	202.89 (.000)

GCI	-37.12 (.000)	-7.25 (.000)	165.02 (.000)
TR	-12.48 (.000)	-0.62 (.26)	113.94 (.002)

Result of stationary test presented in table shows that all variables are stationary at level except for Trade (TR) for IPS. Overall results confirmed that there is no unit root problem in the present study and we can proceed further.

5 Result analyses & discussions

The model summary of hierarchical regression analysis for six individual models is presented in table 6. So, we ran six individual hierarchical regressions for six dimensions of LP. In the first step of the regression we have used dummy variable & volume of trade (% of GDP) to control our model. GCI is used in combination with dummy variable & volume of trade in second step of the regression. The purpose of the step/block is to investigate the variation of the significance of model improvement adding variables in different stages. The standardized beta weight/coefficients for each model have been shown. Asterisk figures in the () indicates the t value with significant impact level. F-value R-square, adjusted R-square and the change in R-square have also been presented.

Standardized beta coefficients of first step for control variables trade (.240) & dummy (.553) in model-1 are presented along with t-value respectively 4.40 and 10.14. All t-values are significant at 0.001 levels. R^2 , and adjusted R^2 of first step are .404 & .398 respectively. F-values for both block-1 and 2 in the regression are also significant. Model development indicator GCI is used in the 2nd step to extract the change in the model variation. R^2 in the 1st step of the regression is 40% whereas it is 66% in the 2nd step. The change of R^2 is $(.667-.404) = .263$ that is 26% increase in R^2 after using GCI. so, R^2 value increase is relatively high and it implies the improvement of efficiency of customs clearance process (ECCP) using global competitiveness indicators. Both block-1 and block-2 of the regression are statistically significant in model-1. Beta coefficients for all variables in the second step of the regression in the first model are also statistically meaningful. Considering R^2 (26%) change, it is evident in the research that addition of global competitiveness index in logistics performance can improve the dimension of the model.

Table 6: Result of hierarchical regression analysis

Model	Variables	Block-1	Block-2
Model-1-ECCP	TR	.240 (4.40*)	.121 (2.87*)
	DV	.553 (10.14*)	.364 (8.37*)
	GCI		.566 (12.70*)
F-value		69.41*	136.33*
R^2		.404	.667
Adjusted R^2		.398	.662
ΔR^2			.263*
Model-2-QTTINFRT	TR	.189 (3.49*)	.063 (1.59)
	DV	.586 (10.82*)	.387 (9.43*)

	GCI			.594	(14.12*)
F-value		71.98*		160.99*	
R ²		.413		.703	
Adjusted R ²		.407		.699	
Δ R ²		.413*		.290*	
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Model-3-CPS	TR	.180	(3.31*)	.083	(1.76***)
	DV	.587	(10.80*)	.434	(8.88*)
	GCI			.458	(9.15*)
F-value		70.76*		94.12*	
R ²		.408		.581	
Adjusted R ²		.403		.574	
Δ R ²		.408*		.172*	
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Model-4-CQLS	TR	.143	(2.64*)	.028	(.648)
	DV	.603	(11.10*)	.420	(9.49*)
	GCI			.548	(12.10*)
F-value		71.16*		129.97*	
R ²		.410		.657	
Adjusted R ²		.404		.651	
Δ R ²		.410*		.247*	
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Model-5-FS	TR	.114	(2.69*)	.035	(.815)
	DV	.615	(11.50*)	.443	(9.85*)
	GCI			.515	(11.17*)
F-value		76.12*		123.02*	
R ²		.426		.644	
Adjusted R ²		.421		.639	
Δ R ²		.426*		.218*	
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Model-6-CT	TR	.140	(2.64*)	.027	(.643)
	DV	.627	(11.34*)	.447	(10.42*)
	GCI			.537	(12.21*)
F-value		80.17*		141.76*	
R ²		.439		.676	
Adjusted R ²		.433		.671	
Δ R ²		.439*		.237*	

Standardized regression coefficients are reported. Within cells, the 1st row figures are the beta coefficients, figures in () are the t-values significant at * p<0.001, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.1

Beta coefficients for both block-1 (.189, .586) and block-2 (.063, .387 & .594) in model-2 for all variables are statistically meaningful except the control variable trade (.063) which is not significant at 2nd block of the regression. However, F-values (71.98, 160.99) of both stages are statistically meaningful too. R² in the first stage is .413 which is .699 in the second stage after adding GCI in the regression. The change in R² is (.699-.413) = 29% that means the dimension of the logistics performance model could be increased by 29% if the competitiveness index is added in the model development strategies. Value of R² indicates that 70% variations in quality of trade and transport related infrastructure (QTTINFRT) might be explained the model. However, the impact of port facilities (DV) is statistically meaningful as well. That is to say ports are very crucial in performing economic activities related to quality of logistics services,

competitive price shipments, commodities or passengers transferred between land and water carriers.

The change in R^2 in model-3 is 17% which is 40% at the first stage & 57% in the 2nd stage of the regression. The increase in the dimension of the model is incurred after the addition of the main variable GCI in the last stage. That is to say, the dimension of competitive price shipments could be increased using the moderator effect of GCI on the performance quality. R^2 change and beta coefficients along with F-values (70.76, 94.12) for both stages are statistically significant. Standardized beta coefficients of block-1 (.180, .587) and block-2 (.083, .434, .458) with t-values are meaningful. The impact of GCI on model 4 is statistically significant too. Standardized beta coefficients of Trade (.143 and .028), dummy (.603 and .420) and GCI (.548) are statistically significant except coefficient of trade at 2nd block of the regression while F-values (71.16, 129.97) are meaningful. The change of R^2 is 24 % which increased from 41% in the 1st block to 65% in the second block.

However, the impact of trade volume both on model-5 and model-6 in the 2nd block of regression is not significant though both of the model produce overall meaningful impact on logistics performance dimensions. R^2 for model-5 is .426 and .644 with a change of 21% while .439 and .676 for model-6 with 23% increase. The change in R^2 is relatively high and it indicates the addition of the global competitiveness index in the model can improve the logistics performance in Asian countries. F-values of model-5 (F-values 76.12, 123.02) & model-6 (F-values 80.17, 141.76) are significantly meaningful.

Several diagnostic tests have been performed to check the validity of the selected models. In terms of goodness-of-fit, we find six models of logistics performance dimensions fitted the data well, where overall F-statistics are highly significant and almost all R^2 are more than 65 that suggest the 65% variations of logistics performance can be explained by the specified explanatory variables. Moreover, we considered multicollinearity issue in the regressions though our panel data sets are time series but with gaps and stationary at level. A rule of thumb for multicollinearity that is sometimes given for the tolerance and the VIF is that the tolerance should not be less than 0.1, and that therefore the VIF should not be greater than 10 (Miles, 2005). We find our model free from multicollinearity problems since none of the variance inflation factors (VIF) are greater than 10 as rules of thumb proposed by O' Brien, 2007 and García, 2015, VIF values in our models are 1; whereas tolerance are greater than 0.1 and close to 1. Excessive focusing on the effects of multicollinearity on sample fluctuations of parameters, however, can seduce researchers into ignoring other factors (O'brien, 2007). We checked normal probability plot of the regression and found to be normal too.

To explore the significance of GCI on logistics performance indicators, we proposed six regressions models for Asian countries by using volume of trade and Dummy as controlling factors. Both of our control variables have meaningful impact on logistics dimensions. Port facilities (DV) such as warehousing, transshipment, piers, refueling, repairs, and seagoing

vessels entering are the dominant criteria because ports facilities constitute vital economic activity in the hinterland of coastal areas. So, Asian countries can concentrate on the crucial connection between sea and land transport along with bilateral trade development. The moderate relation among efficiency of customs clearance process (ECCP), quality of trade and transport related infrastructure, competitive price shipments, competence and quality of logistics services, frequency of shipments, consignments tracing and tracking and global competitiveness index have been demonstrated in the results. Regression result demonstrates that efficiency of customs clearance process can be developed by undertaking the competitiveness factors in consideration. An efficient customs clearance process is one dimension of the logistics services sector, among others, essential for facilitating international trade in goods while an inefficient customs clearance process can hinder trade (Gani, 2016). Global competitive factors like macroeconomic stability, infrastructure & connectivity, health and labor market efficiency are very crucial for Asian economy. Greater labor market flexibility can promote productivity and productivity can lead to trade and transport related infrastructure development and thus impacts on logistics capability. Global competitive factors like infrastructure & connectivity may reduce shipment time and risk enabling consignments tracing and tracking flexibility. The mild impact of GCI on competitive price shipment should be thought as R^2 is only 58% in comparison with others. If the countries target to the top level of performance, over all dimensions of logistics performance should be revised using GCI factors along with trade performance and port facilities.

6 Conclusions

Validating the existence of global competitiveness index in influencing logistics performance of Asia is an empirical debate. While many research showed impact of GCI only on individual country, the contribution of this study is the demonstration of importance of GCI in increasing logistics performance of whole Asia. Since we found the relationship of logistics performance (LP) and GCI to be meaningful, the six models will be extended to investigate the role of global competitiveness for Asian logistics capabilities. The performance of six dimensions of LP found to be developed by visualizing and optimizing all relevant logistic processes such as speed, simplicity and predictability of formalities, border control management, shipping time and price. Quality services like transportation, warehouse and efficiency of communication, employee training and education, technological readiness should be taken into account. GCI ingredients however, work as the catalyst in the models those might be taken to explain logistics performance.

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Acknowledgments

This research is financially supported by the Project of Humanities and Social Sciences Research of Hebei Provincial Department of Education: Research on the Economic System of Green, low-carbon & Circular Development. (Reference No. ZD201902).

Conflicts of Interest

No conflict of interest to be declared.

Appendix A: Country list

Afghanistan	Hong Kong	S. Korea	Oman	Thailand
Armenia	Georgia	Kuwait	Pakistan	Turkey
Azerbaijan	India	Kyrgyzstan	Philippines	UAE
Bahrain	Indonesia	Laos	Qatar	Uzbekistan
Bangladesh	Israel	Lebanon	S. Arabia	Vietnam
Bhutan	Japan	Malaysia	Singapore	
Cambodia	Jordan	Mongolia	S. Lanka	
China	Kazakhstan	Nepal	Tajikistan	

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